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Administrators' Conflict Management and Strategies
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Abstract:

This study seeks to identify key elements to workplace conflict. A descriptive phenomenological design, a qualitative method used by the researchers to gain a deeper knowledge of the phenomenon, was used. The experiences of the informants led to the development of five themes. The themes supported the necessity of conflict management, emphasizing its significance particularly in the relationship between administrators and those they supervise. Additionally, their individual families might find it significant. Lessons on how to prevent disputes in every circumstance or job may be learned from the many themes. Hurtful comments, misunderstandings, failing to handle obligations, and failing to delegate jobs were the causes of the conflicts. But these disputes were successfully resolved owing to effective communication and the mediation of friends and coworkers. Conflict can be supported and influenced by effective conflict management. The third theme is "Well-managed conflicts are opportunities for cooperation." The fourth theme is that handling conflict helps people develop as people. Theme No. 5: Conflict situations should be handled completely.

Keywords: Management, Administrators, Leadership, Conflict

Introduction

Conflicts can occur in any business, organizations, and groups that may be formal or informal and are made up of people from different backgrounds owing to stress, temperaments, philosophies, and personalities that go beyond a certain threshold. Some of these variables are brought about by individual differences in temperament, access to social resources, and the efficacy of coping mechanisms applied to the stressful situation. There may be some relationships that will necessarily be fraught with difficulties in a school setting or workplace where people work closely together and whose functions require regular communication (Sasan, 2021).

A conflict is a conflict between two or more parties concerning the activities utilized to attain particular goals (Starks & Brown Trinidad, 2007). People express divergent views on how to satiate their wants and interests, and they encounter obstacles to accomplishing their goals. Due to the enormous spectrum of possible differences among individuals, conflict arises between people in all types of human relationships and in all social contexts. Additionally, it happens within an organization, whether it is in the military, government, banks, or even churches. Shared resources, divergent viewpoints, conflicting expectations for roles and job activities, individual methods, and organizational development are all part of this.

Conflict occurs when there is an imbalance between one's own self-interest and those of others. Conflict is regarded as an incompatibility of behaviors or aims amongst people (Strathern, 1985). People and organizations who don't engage in conflict are either in denial, don't genuinely care about other people, or are just apathetic. Every conflict stems from the fundamental human ideals of respect and justice not being acknowledged. Conflicted individuals believe that their own gains are the other party's losses. Understanding and acknowledging conflict is a constructive way to approach it since it can eliminate imbalance, promote growth and development, and enhance relationships (Redpath, 2013).

Conflict is an inevitable part of modern existence, according to Kieliszek (2019), because of contemporary trends. Organizational conflict is inevitable as a result of the following major trends: continual change, more employee diversity, an increase in virtual and self-managed teams, a decrease in face-to-face communication due to technology, and a globalized economy. According to them, a conflict arises when one party believes that the interests of the other party are being resisted or negatively impacted. Our comprehension and appreciation of our interaction with reality and of human activity are fundamentally based on the concept of conflict. Conflict can be viewed as a broad philosophical category that refers to the struggle of power against power as everything strives to become manifest or it can simply be seen as a distinct category of social behavior, where two parties are attempting to obtain an object that neither of them can have. A variety of behaviors are involved when dealing with conflict. One is to confront the other person head-on and have a civil conversation. However, aggressive behavior—including the use of profanity, physical harm, verbal threats, shunning the other party in public, planting rumors to damage the other party's reputation, bringing a lawsuit against the other party, and in the case of labor unions, picketing or going on strike—typically occurs when emotions are high (Kerkvliet, 2019).

Rafferty and Griffin (2004) identified five factors that contribute to conflict, including relationships, data, interests, structural factors, and values. When there is a perceived imbalance in the distribution or sharing of power and resources, as well as the presence of competing interests, conflict can arise in relationships between individuals when one party is less capable of recognizing and meeting the needs or interests of the other. It can also arise between groups. Conflict can even occur when data are not misinterpreted. Needs typically drive interests, and conflict arises when needs are not addressed. Conflicts often have structural reasons that involve societal structures, processes, or human organizations. When different parties place different priorities on the same values, conflict can also arise (Sasan & Rabillas, 2022).

Every conflict does not have to have a bad outcome. It can also act as a catalyst or driver for the development of a bond between two people or organizations. Conflict resolution in both personal and professional relationships can be achieved via open discourse, sincere communication, and the tenets of respect, trust, and care (Guenzi & Nijssen, 2020).

Maintaining current with new developments and developing solutions fit for new risks and opportunities are made possible by effective conflict management. Conflicts and problems might have actual or fictitious causes (Sasan & Baritua, 2022). Over time, a conflict may escalate (become stronger) or deescalate (weaken). Be proactive conflict managers or allow conflict to manage you. Conflict of the right kinds and intensity motivates people to make wise choices. This study is being conducted under this assumption.

A theoretical Stance

To eliminate bias and prevent data contamination without prior or previous information, this investigation is not grounded in any theory. However, themes were created based on the informants' individual experiences. If developed further, the themes can be used to the handling of disputes in any industry, organization, or family.

Philosophical Stance

The philosophical stance seeks to explore the study's philosophical underpinnings. It is necessary to give background on the perceptual perspective, on what to search for, and on how to methodologically characterize the conflict as a phenomenon in order to perform the study.

Existentialism was chosen as the study's philosophical perspective. The distinctiveness of each person is emphasized by existentialism. Soren Kierkegaard, the founder of existentialism, believed that human existence is always and exclusively autonomous and never social. According to Waytz, et al., man is an individual who functions, evolves, develops, makes decisions, experiences pain, and has strong emotions. He also faces God as an individual (2010).

Atheist existentialist Jean-Paul Sartre claimed that existence precedes essence, meaning that existence creates essence. The nature of people is a result of existence. Man is born without human nature (essence). Man is his own creator; he formed himself into what he is. Only what a man wills himself to be determines who he is. All that a man is is what he makes of himself. What is meant by will is that man makes a conscious selection of what he will be. Will in this context denotes a decision. Man has the freedom to choose when he makes a decision. Man must take responsibility for the consequences of his decisions because they have an impact on other people in addition to himself (Sasan, et al., 2022). For instance, if a man decides to steal and is successful, it is advantageous to him

but harmful to the victim of the theft. According to Gordon, if a guy decides to become a teacher, all those who will learn under him will benefit (2010).

Additionally, existentialist embraces the belief that thinking begins with human existence, or the human situation. It places a strong emphasis on the individual's uniqueness, particular concern, and concreteness of experience (Kilag, et al., 2022). Existentialism typically upholds the concepts of personal autonomy, human dignity, romantic love, and creative endeavor. The most crucial of these, in the opinion of, are individual dignity and freedom of choice (Tranvåg,, et. al., 2013).

Existentialism places a high priority on freedom of choice, which is heavily influenced or determined by a number of circumstances, including the following:

1. Family influence, particularly that of the parents. Moral principles are typically taught at home, and the person uses them to help him decide what is good and wrong. Parents can have an impact on a person's career choice.
2. Influence of friends and colleagues. The way a person acts in social situations is frequently impacted by his or her friends. This is true especially in the barkada system. He participates in anything his friends or barkada want to do.
3. A commitment to religion. The individual frequently follows the teachings of his own faith while making a moral decision.
4. Social acceptance. Social acceptance is a significant factor in choosing. There are many people who always try to conform to social norms.
5. Societal norms. This is comparable to social acceptance. This is true because societally accepted cultural practices are frequently present.
6. Monetary situation. Choice is significantly constrained by financial situation. For instance, a lot of young individuals wish to continue their education but are unable to do so due to poverty. Many students also opt for courses that are comparably less expensive than their top choices. Suppose someone wishes to pursue a career in medicine. It costs too much money and takes too long to complete. He decides to pursue education instead because it is less expensive.
7. characteristics of the mind, particularly intelligence. Despite having a strong desire, one may not be able to continue their studies at college due to their poor mental capacity, particularly if they perform poorly on the government-sponsored college entrance exam.
8. Sex. Sex also restricts options. Because of their inability to carry children and other feminine traits, women's options for enlisting in the military are still relatively limited. This makes it difficult for them to be effective on the front lines of battle. They perform farm chores less efficiently as well.
9. Fitness and good health. The physical test must be passed in order to join the military, regardless of one's desire to do so.
10. Education. Decision-making is significantly influenced by education. In general, a person's response to a circumstance depends on the quality and amount of his education. For instance, educated people typically resolve conflicts through the legal system, but uneducated people typically do so through physical conflict. People with education typically select foods that meet their bodies' physiological needs, while people without education typically eat whatever fills their hunger or appetite. People with higher levels of education tend to select life partners who are at least as educated as they are. People with low levels of education tend to pick life partners who are also uneducated.

The youth must, therefore, receive an appropriate education tailored to their levels of intelligence and aptitude. They must also be instilled with respectable moral, ethical, spiritual, and social values. They must also receive training in appropriate civic and governmental affairs, good human and social relations, and appropriate occupational skills.

Research Methodology

Design

In order to better interpret and comprehend the phenomenon, the authors of this study used a descriptive phenomenological design, a qualitative method. The investigation's use of phenomenological design is appropriate because it aims to identify and comprehend the fundamental causes of the conflict, which is seen as a social phenomenon. Phenomenology advances knowledge of social life and human existence. Life's themes and lessons can be learned from one's lived experiences.

Informants

The seven informants were Toledo City's school administrators, and they were chosen through the use of the criterion sampling technique, a particular kind of purposive sampling design. The criteria were based on the number of years of administration, having experienced the phenomenon, and being able to describe how it felt.

Data Collection and Analysis

The investigation's focus in the phenomenological design is on rich first-person accounts. The researchers used semistructured face-to-face interviews, written narratives, diaries, online interviews, note-taking, videotaped and audiotaped interviews, as well as other methods for data collection to better grasp a comprehensive understanding. To delve deeper into the participants' opinions, lived experiences, beliefs, and emotions, the researchers used open-ended survey questionnaires. This project's exploration of the real-world experiences of these administrators would greatly benefit from the self-evaluation and self-report interviews that were administered.

In the end, the narrative stories revealed the participants' experiences in a chronology, placing them in their personal, social, and historical contexts and highlighting the key themes they contained. A story is lived and told in a narrative inquiry (Clandinin, 2006).

Results and Findings

Management of Conflicts

In this, Toledo City school administrators who served as informants provide narrative recollections of their personal experiences with conflict management. The researchers conducted in-person interviews with the administrators.

Conflicts could be divided into two categories: structural conflicts and interpersonal conflicts. The interpersonal problems they had with their colleagues supervisors and their families were structural difficulties they encountered when carrying out their tasks and obligations. The narratives of experiences included the informants' experiences as pivotal participants in situations of conflict.

The structural conflicts were first discussed followed by the interpersonal

STRUCTURAL CONFLICTS

Informant A

I had a conflict with some of my coworkers. I never anticipated that the conversation we were having—we were officemates—would turn sour.

We were talking about various leadership concepts. We battled over issues to the point where we forgot our positions and the etiquette that we had to respect, rather than arriving to improved leadership and management techniques. She spoke with a loud voice that was quite upsetting. I also ignored professional manners and art and spoke to her.

It was an extremely humiliating situation. When our chief came over and ordered us to halt, we stopped panicking. We didn't speak or even look at each other for three days. I informed the president. We acknowledged our errors, and the school president assisted us in communicating with one another. We never laid blame on one another, and thanks to the president's counsel, the conflict was resolved. There was a brief moment of reunion, tears were shed, and the relationship was once again peaceful. The issue was resolved through mediation, but we must be careful to maintain equilibrium.

Informant B described how she had personally faced conflicts with both her coworkers and some of her family.

If we try to track our time, I noticed that we spend a lot more time at work or in the office than at home. I can also remark that our coworkers or office mates, regardless of how close or intimate a relationship they may have, may also be the cause of misunderstanding, unfavorable, and incorrect interpretation of the rules, concepts, and ideologies introduced by the division through the school head.

To further explain, I had an argument with one of my closest friends in the division office over how we were supposed to interpret some new policies that were communicated to us. We made the argument that I was correct and she was wrong in an effort to defend ourselves. She also asserted that I was mistaken and that she was correct. We got into a heated dispute that day, and it was never resolved. The next day, I texted her on her cellphone in the nicest possible way, suggesting that we clear up our confusion over lunch. I invited two of my coworkers. After the scrumptious lunch, I started a chat, and we both acknowledged our shortcomings. Since I thought that unresolved issues would turn into personal grudges that could impair our work and give the impression that we lost the heavenly and divine gifts, I invited everyone to sit down together during lunch so that we could each personally resolve the issue.

I had also had conflicts with my relatives, especially when one of them was staying at our house with the family. I don't mind her and I just said yes to stop her because I want our family relationships to stay the way they are. Then, I turned to another conversation that would suit her.

Filipinos are quite clannish, it is true. In-laws, cousins, and other relatives live with people. We must always seek mediation from other individuals, such as our office mates, in order to resolve conflicts because they are our trusted everyday companions and we understand them. Understanding and showing respect for our relatives are essential. Blood is thicker than water, as is sometimes remarked.

I had seen that there is sufficient time for conflict resolution and that our proper respect is crucial. Both locations had a calm and welcoming tone as everything had returned to normal. Relationships with family and friends are reestablished.

Informant C

My daughter came one late night, I remembered. She didn't even seek for permission or to go where she was going. Since it was obvious that I should have some questions for her given how late she had arrived, my daughter yelled at me yet I refrained from reprimanding and instead maintained my composure while speaking softly. I advised her that parents should inquire. She shouted back at me. We kept arguing, and I yelled at them.

In the office, professional envy was extremely prevalent. Others thanked me for helping a group of children win a Science competition, while others did not. There was envy.

These conflicts were not solved immediately, but in a matter of four days all were definitely settled. It depends on how serious or how deep the conflict is to resolve it. One of the things that helped resolve conflicts was effective communication. The conflict was resolved, bringing back harmony in the home and at the office as well as friendship and good relations. I had also seen that stronger or closer ties were more prevalent.

Misunderstanding of issues and work delegation can cause conflict based on the narration of Informant C. I never imagined that three years as a principal would expose me to many groups and personalities of teachers, students, and other people. I had conflicts with a few of my coworkers at the school and officemates.

I firmly believed that correctly delegating tasks out of jealousy could lead to or even start a fight. How bizarre that is I acknowledge that my teacher and I were both impacted by this misunderstanding of task delegation. Of course, with the assistance of our school president, the dispute was resolved for nearly a week. In an effort to end the conflict altogether, I also had the fortitude to speak honestly to my coworkers.

My priorities are my family and my coworkers at the school since I value both of them. I greatly valued them, and I never anticipated that there would be a conflict. The problem can be resolved by talking to the parties involved. I think the harmony and friendship were eventually restored. Conflict shouldn't continue to be a problem. youthful and vibrant.

Informant D

I wish to work with serious individuals who can take on assigned obligations and who have experience with various life circumstances. I enjoy conversing openly with those that are courageous and aware of societal trends. I became bored among people who were closed-minded and lacked a grasp of their obligations or communal duties. I pay close attention to how other people act, interact, and decide because else we can have a conflict. Others relied on the level of conflict we had, and the conflict I had lasted for three weeks.

I prefer us to resolve the issue and reassess ourselves rather than having others mediate an already-existing problem. Face-to-face communication was used to try and resolve the issue by ourselves. I acknowledge that the seriousness of a conflict determines how to resolve it. However, because we are professionals, professionalism and compassionate feelings should take complete precedence over friendship and harmonious relationships. The progressive office or workplace is distinguished by everyone's camaraderie, peace, and the aroma of vivacious and friendly staff who trust one another and are not dominated by any conflict.

Informant E

The final informant was informant E. Despite having six years of experience as a school administrator, she had a tale to share about the management of conflict that she had encountered, just like the other informants.

The conflict I had with my coworkers happened right there at work or at the division office and was brought on by favoritism in task delegation as well as by unfavorable or unfounded accusations that did not respect the seniority rule and the qualifications of the parties involved.

The "whom you know" mentality still exists when assigning tasks. As a result, there was a conflict between myself and my coworkers, including the vice presidents of our institution.

When I delegate tasks to the program supervisors, I always do so in accordance with the values of duty, truth, and responsibility rather than out of favor and friendliness. Fairness must be maintained when assigning duties. Doing this might be a cause of workplace strife.

Unresolved conflicts make it difficult for the workplace to operate effectively. To ensure fairness and allow our Division to operate and provide better services to teachers, I made every effort to resolve the teachers' conflicts.

The task delegation issue was quickly fixed. It took approximately a week for the false accusation, and those unsolved issues were simply forgotten and moved on by the passage of time.

Informant F

INTERPERSONAL CONFLICTS

This school administrator is extremely forthright in admitting that, although being well into her forties, she occasionally had conflicts with her family, friends, and coworkers in the office. She described:

I acknowledge that I brought several opportunities that helped me develop my advisory talents. My work ethic is really strong, and service is my secret weapon. I treasured the company of my classmates and pals. I have been married to my career, which I have always loved.

I had a conflict with my coworker who was a teacher and who was also my best buddy at work since we had misunderstood several important work-related concerns. This type of dispute was referred to as avoiding conflict since we spent three years not communicating with one another. I refrained from taking full responsibility because I knew it wasn't all my fault. Due to misunderstandings that persisted for three years, I was separated from the location. One of our coworkers in the same workplace took the time to schedule a genuine conversation with us. The schedule was created after business hours, only a few meters from the Division Office. Despite the fact that the friendship was not quite the same as before, our friend helped us mend the divide. However, communication and unity have persisted up until this point.

Situations involving conflict shouldn't be disregarded. To keep the actions and items in check and in the right order, the parties should find ways and means to settle the dispute.

Informant G

The following is a sharing of Informant G's conflict management experiences:

Due to the complexity of the subject matter assigned to me, which is completely different from the duties and tasks assigned to my coworkers, I typically work with groups of individuals. My coworkers commented on my work and how I performed in my own field of expertise. I overheard some unfavorable remarks that hurt my ego. The conflict sprang from my quiet, which persisted for four weeks.

However, given that we share an office, I did not want that circumstance to continue. They and I were in constant communication, and this allowed us to completely close the distance of dispute. The normal friendship and peaceful relationship were fully restored when the conflict was resolved. Issue that could lead to an explosion and leave the situation unsettled. Keep your composure, exercise caution, and work toward a win-win outcome.

PREDOMINANT THEMES

Theme No. 1

Conflict is a defect.

awareness of the appropriate language to employ in a given circumstance. We must all be conscious of the nature and traits of the persons we are speaking with. Its character, including their strengths and shortcomings, must be evaluated. If at all feasible, use courteous language or expressions because what is said or written can reveal a lot about our personalities. To avoid offending other people's sensibilities, we must exercise caution. It's challenging to untangle what had been spoken. Our character, which shapes our personality, is how other people judge us.

Theme No. 2

Conflict can be supported and influenced by effective conflict management.

The defining characteristics of a person include their character, temperament, and personality. Always be moderate and adaptable when faced with divergent viewpoints, and work to achieve a consensus. Always consider the long-term effects of any activity before taking it.

Theme No. 3

Conflicts that are handled well provide opportunity for collaboration.

There is no rivalry among group members, and there is no method to determine who is the greatest. Everyone does, however, have the opportunity to compete against his or her own record in order to build the essential potentials to reach the pinnacle of achievement.

Theme No. 4

Conflict resolution fosters the growth of personality and character.

When a problem is resolved and restored at the 50-0 scheme, a higher level of friendship is established. Making an opponent your friend is a strategy for defeating an opponent. Try to get to know each of your coworkers personally. Never make promises, threats, or harsh remarks out of haste or carelessness because you can come to regret them. Express your sincere gratitude for their integrity and honesty at all times, and be willing to take constructive criticism and ideas.

Theme No. 5

Conflict resolution should be a top priority. Conflict situations should be handled civilly. Learn the skills of negotiation, conversation, and fair compromise to reach a "win-win" outcome. Never forget how to interact with others. To prevent further escalation of emotionally charged and extremely volatile situations, master the art of self-control.

Conclusion

The seven Toledo City administrators' individual experiences were studied using phenomenology to acquire pertinent information. The researchers interviewed each of the seven administrators informally as the primary method of data gathering. Concerning the handling of disputes they had encountered both at work and with their families, questions were posed to the administrators about their experiences, sentiments, and convictions. According to the study's findings, although conflict is unavoidable because of human nature and is influenced by both external and internal variables, it may still be controlled by making changes. To reduce any risky implications within the home and workplace situations, the program supervisors should try to minimize any unfavorable components of the program.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made to improve the research:

1. Every time a conflict occurs, whether at business or at home, it needs to be resolved or managed skillfully to preserve the harmonious relationships between the parties involved.
2. There are numerous causes of conflict and ways to end it. Incompatible value systems, job overlap, rivalry, poor communication, ambiguous policies, unmet expectations, and unresolved or repressed conflicts are the precursors.
3. Conflict resolution in the schools where they are assigned is the main focus and responsibility of the school heads.
4. The office or workplace must provide a location for team-building exercises. These pursuits can lessen boredom and exhaustion as well as prevent or manage potential workplace problems.
5. Implementing the improvement suggestions is recommended.
6. The study may be repeated in additional workplaces, institutions of higher learning, districts, or divisions.

Reference

- Clandinin, D. J. (2006). Narrative inquiry: A methodology for studying lived experience. *Research studies in music education, 27*(1), 44-54.
- Gordon, T. (2010). *Teacher effectiveness training: The program proven to help teachers bring out the best in students of all ages*. Crown Archetype.
- Guenzi, P., & Nijssen, E. J. (2020). Studying the antecedents and outcome of social media use by salespeople using a MOA framework. *Industrial Marketing Management, 90*, 346-359.
- Kerkvliet, B. J. T. (2019). Speaking Out in Vietnam. In *Speaking Out in Vietnam*. Cornell University Press.
- Kieliszek, Z. (2019). Future Conflicts Are Inevitable: Causes of Interpersonal Conflicts According to Immanuel Kant and Thomas R. Malthus. *Philosophy and Cosmology, 22*(22), 152-161.
- Kilag, O. K. T., Ignacio, R., Lumando, E. B., Alvez, G. U., Abendan, C. F. K., Quiñanola, N. M. P., & Sasan, J. M. (2022). ICT Integration in Primary School Classrooms in the time of Pandemic in the Light of Jean Piaget's Cognitive Development Theory. *International Journal of Emerging Issues in Early Childhood Education, 4*(2), 42-54.
- Rafferty, A. E., & Griffin, M. A. (2004). Dimensions of transformational leadership: Conceptual and empirical extensions. *The leadership quarterly, 15*(3), 329-354.
- Redpath, S. M., Young, J., Evely, A., Adams, W. M., Sutherland, W. J., Whitehouse, A., ... & Gutierrez, R. J. (2013). Understanding and managing conservation conflicts. *Trends in ecology & evolution, 28*(2), 100-109.
- Sasan, J. M., & Baritua, J. C. (2022). Distance learning as a learning modality for education during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Science and Education, 3*(8), 35-44.
- Sasan, J. M., Barquin, A. M. E., Alestre, N. A., Librea, A., & Zamora, R. M. (2022). Karl Marx on technology and alienation. *Science and Education, 3*(9), 228-233.

Sasan, J. M., & Rabillas, A. R. (2022). Enhancing English proficiency for Filipinos through a multimedia approach based on constructivist learning theory: a review. *Science and Education*, 3(8), 45-58.

Sasan, J. M. V. (2021). The Social Contract Theories of Thomas Hobbes and John Locke: Comparative Analysis.

Starks, H., & Brown Trinidad, S. (2007). Choose your method: A comparison of phenomenology, discourse analysis, and grounded theory. *Qualitative health research*, 17(10), 1372-1380.

Strathern, M. (1985). Discovering social control. *JL & Soc'y*, 12, 111.

Tranvåg, O., Petersen, K. A., & Nåden, D. (2013). Dignity-preserving dementia care: a metasynthesis. *Nursing Ethics*, 20(8), 861-880.

Waytz, A., Gray, K., Epley, N., & Wegner, D. M. (2010). Causes and consequences of mind perception. *Trends in cognitive sciences*, 14(8), 383-388.